

CRISPR/Cas9 genome engineering in PDAC: From preclinical studies to translation and clinical research

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ABSTRACT

CRISPR/Cas9 technology has emerged as a powerful tool in pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma cancer (PDAC) research, facilitating the study of genes involved in cell signaling pathways, proliferation, migration, invasion, and chemotherapy resistance. In this review, we discuss the evolution of CRISPR technologies from sophisticated editing techniques to broad screening methods, examine the utility of isogenic models and genetically engineered mouse models (GEMMs). We also explore how CRISPR/Cas9 screens can reveal immune-tumor cell interactions, highlighting the multifaceted role of this technology in PDAC research. Moreover, we emphasize the use of CRISPR technology in diagnostics for CAR-T cell therapies, where CRISPR/Cas9 enhances the precision of targeting malignant cells while minimizing off-tumor effects.

1. Introduction

The journey of Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats (CRISPR) began with its discovery in bacterial and archaeal genomes, where it serves as a defense mechanism against invasive genetic elements [1]. With the identification of CRISPR-associated (Cas) proteins, CRISPR-Cas technology has revolutionized gene editing, enabling precise manipulation of the genomes of a wide range of organisms, including humans [2,3]. This powerful tool has significant implications in oncology and is also widely used in pancreatic cancer, a malignancy characterized by its aggressive nature and poor prognosis [4].

Pancreatic cancer is one of the most lethal cancers. Despite steady advances in oncology, pancreatic cancer is projected to become the second leading cause of cancer-related deaths, surpassing breast, prostate, and colorectal cancers, because of its late diagnosis and therapy resistance [5,6]. Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) is the most prevalent form of pancreatic cancer, accounting for approximately 85 %

of all histologically classified cases [7]. Only 20 % of the patients present with localized disease and are eligible for surgical resection.

Kirsten rat sarcoma viral oncogene homolog (human symbol: KRAS, mouse symbol: *Kras*), tumor protein p53 (human symbol: TP53, mouse symbol: *Trp53*), cyclin dependent kinase inhibitor 2 A (human symbol: CDKN2A), and SMAD family member 4 (human symbol: SMAD4) mutations are key genetic alterations in PDAC, as revealed by a comprehensive proteogenomic analysis. These mutations impact critical pathways such as KRAS signaling, TP53-mediated DNA damage repair, and epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) [8]. KRAS is the most frequently mutated gene (at least 86 %) in PDAC [9,10], and CRISPR/Cas9 knockout screening has emerged as a powerful tool in this context, revealing genes that directly regulate KRAS function or act as downstream effectors or in parallel pathways. The discovery of some pathways and targets using CRISPR/Cas9 technology has propelled the understanding of KRAS-driven pancreatic cancer and may lead to the development of more effective treatment strategies [11–13]. Given the high mortality rate of PDAC and its resistance to conventional therapies,

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accurately replicating the pathological hallmarks of the disease in pre-clinical models is essential for evaluating therapeutic strategies and informing clinical trial designs. Isogenic models generated using CRISPR technology have facilitated the study of human disease pathology *in vitro*, offering a platform for exploring genetic variations and new therapeutic strategies [14]. Moreover, genetically engineered mouse models (GEMMs) of PDAC faithfully reflect the genetic and biological progression observed in human PDAC, offering a robust experimental platform for investigating tumorigenesis, early disease detection, and evaluation of therapeutic responses [15].

This review focuses on advances in CRISPR/Cas9 technology and its applications in pancreatic cancer, ranging from *in vitro* studies to clinical trials. First, this review provides an overview of the CRISPR/Cas system, its function as immune response in bacteria and archaea, its classification into classes and types, and the different technologies that leverage the CRISPR/Cas9 system. Next, this review discusses how these CRISPR/Cas9 technologies have been applied to pancreatic cancer research and its potential for application in clinical trials. Lastly, this review discusses the limitations of the discussed techniques and possibilities to overcome these limitations.

2. CRISPR/Cas technologies: an overview

The CRISPR-Cas system was originally identified as part of the

immune response in bacteria and archaea where it protects against invading genomes [16–18]. The immune response is characterized by three phases: incorporation, expression, and interference (Fig. 1). During the incorporation (or adaptation) phase, a Cas protein complex binds to the invading genome and incorporates a small fragment into the host CRISPR locus. The invading genome is generally recognized by the presence of a protospacer-adjacent motif (PAM), a short nucleotide sequence that is not found in the host genome and can bind to the Cas protein complex. This protein complex then cleaves a short section of the invading genome, called a protospacer, which is incorporated into the host CRISPR locus as a spacer sequence. During the expression phase, the CRISPR locus is transcribed and processed by a Cas protein or protein complex to form mature CRISPR RNAs (crRNAs). In the interference phase, the crRNA guides recognition of the target sequence and a Cas nuclease (which may be part of the processing Cas complex or is recruited separately) cleaves and thereby inactivates the invading genome. For a more in-depth review of the CRISPR-Cas immune response we refer the reader to the following reviews: [19–21]. Fig. 2

Classification of CRISPR/Cas systems based on sequence similarity clustering, phylogenetic analysis, and experimental data has identified two classes and six types of CRISPR/Cas systems [22,23]. The two classes are differentiated by the composition of the effector complex. In class 1, which contains type I, III, and IV, uses varying combinations of Cas3, Cas5–8, Cas10, and Cas11 to form the effector complex. Class 2,

Fig. 1. Overview CRISPR/Cas immune response. The immune response is characterized by three phases: incorporation, expression, and interference. During the incorporation or adaptation phase parts of the viral genome are incorporated into the CRISPR locus. During the expression phase, the CRISPR locus is transcribed and processed to form a functional CRISPR-crRNA complex. In the last phase, interference, the CRISPR complex recognizes the viral genome and cleaves it to inactivate it.

Fig. 2. Overview of CRISPR techniques used in PDAC. A. Knockout) A Cas9 enzyme guided by a gRNA recognises the target sequence and creates a double-strand break. This break can be repaired by NHEJ resulting in a disrupted gene, or by HR resulting in a functional gene. B. Base editing) A nCas9 enzyme fused with a cytosine or adenine deaminase domain deaminates cytosine or adenine to uracil or inosine, respectively. These are recognised as thymidine and guanine and DDR with replication cements the altered nucleotides. C. Prime editing) nCas9 fused with a reverse transcriptase uses a pegRNA to hybridize to the target region and nick the target strand near the PAM. The primer-binding site of the pegRNA binds to the target strand and serves as primer for the reverse transcriptase to extend the sequence with the desired modification. The result is a dsDNA with mismatched sequence and 5' flap. The flap is cleaved and the DNA repair machinery corrects the mismatched using the novel sequence with modification as template. D. CRISPRa) A dCas9 is guided to the target gene using a gRNA. The dCas9 is fused to a transactivator domain to promote DNA transcription. E. CRISPRi) A dCas9 is guided to the target gene using a gRNA. The dCas9 blocks the transcription machinery and thereby inhibits DNA transcription. Fusion with a repressor domain further enhances gene repression.

containing type II, V, and VI, uses a single protein with multiple domains instead of a protein complex to perform the effector functions (Cas9, Cas12, and Cas13, respectively). Class 2 proteins are widely in gene editing applications and are valued for their streamlined design and robust editing capabilities. The Class 2, type II protein Cas9 is most commonly used and will be the focus of this review although Cas12 and Cas13 systems have recently also been introduced into the gene editing toolkit [24]. The CRISPR/Cas9 system has been adapted for multiple gene editing purposes, a description of the main applications and mechanisms of action is given in the following paragraphs and in Fig. 1.

2.1. CRISPR/Cas9 Single-Knockout

CRISPR/Cas9 can be used to create single gene knockouts, allowing for the direct study of gene function by observing the phenotypic changes that occur in the absence of the gene product. A human codon-optimised version of the Cas9 gene (or Cas9 protein) is introduced into the target cell in combination with a guide RNA (gRNA) [25,26]. This gRNA is a fusion of the crRNA and tracrRNA and is designed to bind to the target sequence. The resulting cleavage by the Cas9 protein creates a double-strand break three nucleotides upstream of the PAM. Depending on the cell cycle phase, this break is repaired by homologous recombination (HR) repair or non-homologous end-joining (NHEJ), the majority of lesions are repaired by NHEJ. The fidelity of NHEJ is low, and it generally results in small insertions or deletions (indels) that disrupt gene function and cause gene knockout. To ensure that all cells have the same mutation, a monoclonal cell line can be established and validated by sequencing to ensure effective knockout. However, the process of establishing a cell line from a single cell poses a significant bottleneck, risking experimental bias if the resultant clone fails to represent the comprehensive diversity of the initial cell population [27]. Additionally, it is crucial to assess the underlying genetic, epigenetic, and phenotypic diversity in the cell population before single-cell isolation to ensure that clones are representative of the pooled population.

2.2. CRISPR/Cas9 HDR

Homology-directed repair (HDR) is a faithful DNA repair pathway that can be leveraged to introduce precise gene edits using the CRISPR/Cas system. The HDR pathway repairs double-strand breaks (DSBs) using a homologous sequence to repair breaks without introducing mutations like the error-prone NHEJ pathway, particularly in the context of CRISPR-induced DSBs [28,29]. During the repair process, double-strand breaks are processed to form single-stranded tails that invade an undamaged DNA duplex, forming a D-loop. High-fidelity polymerases then use this DNA as a template for new DNA synthesis on the damaged strand to restore the missing nucleotides, followed by resolution of the heteroduplex. The HDR pathway is primarily active during the S and G2 phase of the cell cycle when it can use the sister chromatid as a template via a non-crossover mechanism. To leverage this pathway for the introduction of gene edits, a single-stranded oligodeoxynucleotide (ssODN) or single-stranded DNA (ssDNA) is introduced into the cell along with the CRISPR/Cas9 system and gRNA [30, 31]. The ssODN is engineered to be homologous to the target region at both ends of the sequence to enable its use as a repair template but includes the desired edit in the center. This technique can be used to create multi-nucleotide DNA insertions, deletions, and mutations. Incorporation of blocking mutations in the ssODN that prevent recognition and re-cleavage of the altered site [32], combination with NHEJ inhibition [33,34], and modulation of cell cycle phase may improve editing efficiency [35].

2.3. Base editing

The latest developments in base editing have replaced dead Cas9 (dCas9) with Cas9 nickase (nCas9), which induces a nick in the non-edited DNA strand that promotes cellular repair using the edited strand as a template, thereby improving editing efficiency. The base editing system comprises two components that are fused together: a catalytically dCas9 enzyme with gRNA to target the desired nucleotide sequence and open the dsDNA, and a deaminase enzyme to alter the base. Cytosine base editors (CBEs) and adenine base editors (ABEs) can be distinguished. CBEs contain a cytidine deaminase enzyme that deaminates cytosine to uracil (which pairs as thymidine) and a uracil DNA glycosylase (UGI) to protect uracil from removal by base excision repair. ABEs function similarly to CBEs, but contain an adenosine deaminase enzyme that deaminates adenosine to inosine, which is read as guanine.

These two base editing systems make it possible to convert all transition mutations (C→T, T→C, A→G, and G→A) [36–42]. Although base editing simplifies the induction of simple substitutions, off-target effects can occur due to the promiscuous reactivity of the deaminase enzymes used in these editors. These guide RNA-independent off-target mutations primarily arise from the deaminases' activity on both DNA and RNA, especially in regions where single-stranded DNA is accessible, such as during transcription when R-loops form [43]. Base editors (BEs) induce detrimental transcriptional responses and reduce editing efficiency in xenotransplants, causing DNA double-strand breaks and genotoxic byproducts, including deletions and translocations. Cytidine BEs exhibit the strongest effects due to inadequate base excision repair inhibition. Optimized mRNA design mitigates these issues, but BEs still increase nucleotide variant, raising genotoxicity concerns for clinical applications [44].

2.4. Prime editing

Prime editing is an innovative and precise genome-editing technique. This technique uses a complex consisting of a reverse transcriptase fused to nCas9 and a prime-editing guide RNA (pegRNA) to directly alter DNA without inducing double-strand breaks. The 5' region of pegRNA hybridizes to the DNA strand complementary to the target strand, and nCas9 nicks the target strand near the PAM location. The 3' region of pegRNA binds to the target strand at the 5' side of the nick. This double-stranded region serves as a primer for the reverse transcriptase domain, which uses pegRNAs containing the desired modification as a template to extend the sequence. The result is a dsDNA with a mismatched sequence where the modification is and an unhybridized flap containing the original sequence. This flap is cleaved, and the DNA repair machinery repairs mismatched sequence [45]. Prime editing exhibits higher efficiency and fewer off-target effects than traditional CRISPR/Cas9 nucleases, potentially allowing it to address a broader spectrum of genetic variants associated with human diseases [40,45,46].

2.5. CRISPRa and CRISPRi

In addition to gene editing, CRISPR/Cas9 can be used to activate or inhibit gene expression without altering the gene sequence. To activate gene expression (CRISPRa), dCas9 is fused with a transactivation domain, such as VP64, to create a protein that can activate gene expression when targeted to DNA sequences by guide RNA [47,48]. CRISPR interference (CRISPRi) is used to inhibit gene expression. At its simplest, the CRISPRi system is a dCas9 with a gRNA that binds to the promoter or regulatory region of the gene of interest, thereby blocking the transcriptional machinery. dCas9 can be merged with additional transcription repressors to increase transcriptional repression. The CRISPRi machinery can dissociate from the DNA, which means that, unlike CRISPR knockout, repression of expression can be reversed [49]. Compare to CRISPRa and CRISPRi, CRISPR-based epigenome editing tools, including dCas9 fusions with DNA methyltransferases, demethylases, and histone modifiers, have demonstrated high efficiency in modulating gene expression in eukaryotic cells without genetic alteration [50]. These tools target the epigenome by acting as 'writers' to add methyl or acetyl groups, 'erasers' to remove them, and indirectly 'readers' that recognize and respond to epigenetic marks. Histone modifications, such as H3K4 methylation and H3K27 acetylation, are associated with gene activation, while H3K9 and H3K27 methylation are linked to repression [51].

2.6. CRISPR/Cas9 screening

CRISPR/Cas9 screening, facilitated by the simultaneous deployment of multiple sgRNAs, enables the performance of gene knockout, silencing, and activation. It can be applied in analyses ranging from small-scale to comprehensive genome-wide studies to identify genes that

are crucial for specific biological processes or diseases. A library of sgRNAs targeting the genes of interest is transfected into a pool of cells that have been made to stably express Cas9 (alternatively, the Cas9 protein/gene can be transfected alongside the sgRNA library). Using a low multiplicity of infection, it is ensured that each cell only receives a single sgRNA; therefore, only a single gene should be knocked out in each cell. The pooled cell population is then placed under selection pressure (e.g., drugs). After treatment, the cells are collected and sequenced at a high coverage. The presence of each sgRNA is quantified; sgRNAs that target genes that are essential under treatment conditions will have been lost, whereas sgRNAs that target genes that inhibit cell growth under treatment conditions will have been amplified [52].

As CRISPR/Cas9 screening enables simultaneous editing and functional analysis of thousands of genes in a mixed population of cells, offering a rapid screening of gene function compared to other gene-editing technologies [53]. Comparative analysis of 373 single guide RNAs across six cell lines between RNA interference (RNAi) and the CRISPR-Cas9 knockout system revealed equivalent on-target efficiencies for both technologies. However, CRISPR-Cas9 has demonstrated significantly lower susceptibility to off-target effects [54].

Although CRISPR/Cas9 screening has greatly improved efficiency compared to other gene editing technologies, there are also some drawbacks. sgRNAs are highly specific, yet non-specific binding to off-target sequences may occur, leading to the editing of non-target genes, which can reduce the accuracy of experimental results. To prevent this, sgRNA libraries generally include multiple sgRNAs targeting the same gene. The efficiency of CRISPR/Cas9 screening may be affected by cell type and cell cycle status and requires optimization of the experimental conditions for different cells [55].

3. Applications in pancreatic cancer research

3.1. Advancing precision editing in cancer mutations

DNA base editing and prime-editing technologies enhance the scope and capabilities of genomic editing, enabling the correction of disease-causing mutations. In PDAC, base and prime-editing have been used to study the role of KRAS and TP53 mutations in tumorigenesis and to introduce mutations in these genes to overcome drug resistance. Ely et al. designed a Cre-inducible prime editor (Rosa26^{PE2}) to introduce specific Kras mutations in PDAC organoids and mice. They achieved up to 18.4 % editing efficiency for Kras(G12D) in pancreatic organoids and tail tip-derived fibroblasts (TTFs). After optimization of the system, they were able to introduce the Trp53^{R245W} mutation with nearly 100 % editing efficiency in organoids [56]. Won et al. approached the issue of KRAS and TP53 mutations in PDAC from the opposite side by correcting these mutations. They used nanoliposomal particles to transfect the Panc-1 cell line with the editing system and were able to introduce the desired mutation in approximately 50 % of the cells. By adding an anti-epidermal growth factor receptor (human symbol: EGFR, mouse symbol: Egrf) antibody to the nanoliposomal particle, they managed to deliver the editing system to the Panc-1 cells in a Panc-1 xenograft model, where they achieved approximately 60 % editing efficiency. Xenografts with the corrected KRAS mutation were significantly more sensitive to gemcitabine treatment [57].

The PAM is a short conserved sequence motif (2–5 bp) adjacent to the proto-spacer on foreign DNA. In the CRISPR-Cas system, PAMs are essential for recognizing and integrating new spacers into CRISPR arrays, indicating that proto-spacers are not randomly selected but are triggered by the recognition of PAM sequences in the donor molecule. PAMs are specific to different CRISPR-Cas variants, influencing the orientation of spacers in the CRISPR array and the overall efficiency of the immune response [58]. In the study of the *S. thermophilus* CRISPR3/Cas system, the PAM sequence was found to be essential for the interference of plasmid transformation in *E. coli*. Specifically, 5'-NGGNG-3' was identified as a conserved motif required for the

CRISPR3/Cas system to recognize and target the invasive DNA. When PAM sequence was mutated or absent, the CRISPR3/Cas system could no longer effectively interfere with plasmid transformation, indicating that both the proto-spacer and PAM are necessary for CRISPR-encoded immunity [59]. The affinity of Cas9:RNA for non-target DNA is directly proportional to the density of PAM sequences present. Importantly, even if a DNA sequence is fully complementary to the guide RNA, Cas9: RNA will not bind to it if it lacks a nearby PAM. Competition assays further elucidate the mechanism of target recognition. These experiments show that the process of DNA strand separation and the formation of RNA-DNA heteroduplexes begin at the PAM and proceed in a directional manner towards the end of the target sequence. This directional unwinding suggests that the PAM serves as an initial binding site that facilitates the subsequent steps of target recognition [60]. CRISPR-Cas9 selectively targets somatic mutations generating PAMs in pancreatic cancers. Through whole genome sequencing, an average of 417 somatic PAMs per tumor are identified, predominantly in noncoding regions. The researchers designed sgRNAs to target these PAMs, CRISPR-Cas9, guided by these cancer-specific sgRNAs, could selectively induce double-strand breaks(DSBs) in cancer cells, achieving 69–99 % selective cell death in pancreatic cancer cell lines while sparing normal cells. This specificity minimizes off-target effects and enhances the safety of the treatment [61].

3.2. Enhancing KRAS targeting

Owing to its challenging molecular structure, the development of targeted agents against KRAS has been severely lacking until very

recently, and many studies have focused on targeting up- and downstream effectors instead [62].

Several studies have used CRISPR/Cas9 knockout screening to identify targets that enhance targeted inhibition of KRAS pathway proteins (Fig. 3). A genome-wide CRISPR loss-of-function screen in combination with KRAS^{G12D} inhibitor MRTX1133 in PDAC cell line ASPC1 found that depleted genes either directly regulated KRAS function (e.g., Rac guanine nucleotide exchange factor 1(human symbol: SOS1) and growth factor receptor bound protein 2(human symbol: GRB2)), acted as downstream effectors (B-Raf proto-oncogene, serine/threonine kinase(human symbol: BRAF), mitogen-activated protein kinase 3(human symbol: MAPK3), and FOS like 1, AP-1 transcription factor subunit(human symbol: FOSL1)), or were associated with parallel pathways (EGFR). Knockdown of EGFR and FOSL1 by RNAi significantly enhanced MRTX1133 efficacy. Similarly, the combination of the EGFR inhibitor gefitinib and MRTX1133 significantly enhanced the cytostatic response [63].

Ozkan-Dagliyan et al. used a 525-compound chemical library and CRISPR genetic screens identify synergistic combinations with the pan-RAF inhibitor LY3009120 and identified multiple inhibitors of EGFR/HER2(erb-b2 receptor tyrosine kinase 2) and the PI3K-AKT (phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate 3-kinase catalytic subunit alpha-AKT serine/threonine kinase 1) signaling pathways. RAFi(pan-RAF inhibitor)/ERKi(ERK inhibitor, ERK:Extracellular-signal-regulated kinases) induced insensitivity to negative feedback loss and system failures, including diminished ERK signaling and FOSL1, MYC(MYC proto-oncogene, bHLH transcription factor, human symbol: MYC) shut-down, and EMT. They concluded that low-dose vertical inhibition of the

Fig. 3. Analysis of different KRAS pathways using CRISPR/Cas9. Genome-wide CRISPR/Cas9 screen in *Kras*^{G12D} murine cell lines, upon treatment with FTS, MRTX1133, CHK1i, RAF+ERKi, identified distinct targets implicated in the regulation of tumor microenvironment, proliferation and apoptosis pathways. Mechanistic target of rapamycin (mTOR), C/EBP homologous protein (CHOP), cancer-related fibroblasts (CAF), Tumor Infiltrating Lymphocytes(TILs), Yes-associated protein 1 (YAP), Transcriptional coactivator with PDZ-binding motif (TAZ), Integrin beta1 (ITGB1), Retinoblastoma (RB), Interferon-gamma(IFN γ), B-cell lymphoma 2 (BCL2), Bcl-2 agonist of cell death (BAD).

RAF-MEK(mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase, MAPKK)-ERK pathway is an effective strategy for treating KRAS-mutant PDAC [64]. Klomp et al. conducted genetic screens to identify modulators of KRAS mutant PDAC sensitivity to ERK inhibitors, and discovered the ATR (ataxia-telangiectasia-mutated-and-Rad3-related kinase)-CHK1(checkpoint kinase 1) DDR(DNA damage response) pathway. CHK1 inhibition alone led to suppression of apoptotic growth in PDAC, which was associated with reduced MYC expression. It also activated ERK and AMPK(AMP-activated protein kinase), enhancing autophagy, suggesting a synergistic effect with CHK1 and ERK inhibitors or chloroquine [11]. A loss-of-function CRISPR/Cas9 screen in combination with the KRAS^{G12G} inhibitor MRTX11330 was performed in two KRAS^{G12D} *in vitro* (HPAC and SUIT2) and *in vivo* (HPAC xenograft) models, and significant depletion of EGFR and PI3K α was found [65]. In contrast to the study by Ozkan-Dagliyan, the combination of MRTX1133 with MEKi or ERKi did not enhance the efficacy. The combination of MRTX1133 with the PI3K α (phosphoinositide 3-kinase alpha) inhibitor BYL-719 or the HER family inhibitor afatinib and cetuximab was synergistic.

Trans-farnesylthiosalicylic acid (salirasib, FTS), a RAS inhibitor, has shown limited efficacy in the past. Endoplasmic-reticulum-associated protein degradation (ERAD) pathway is identified as a potential target for enhancing FTS's therapeutic effect through genome-wide CRISPR synthetic lethality screening, combined treatment with FTS and an ERAD inhibitor, EerI, upregulated unfolded protein response (UPR) markers and induced apoptosis in PDAC cells, suggesting a novel approach to improve FTS efficacy [12].

The combination of KRAS inhibition is synergistic with inhibition of non-KRAS pathways. A genome-wide CRISPR/Cas9 screen in Kras^{G12D} murine cell line 4292 treated with the RAS inhibitor FTS showed significant depletion of multiple genes associated with the endoplasmic reticulum-associated protein degradation (ERAD) pathway [66]. FTS was shown to induce ER stress and was synergistic with the inhibition of ERAD by eyarestatin, which further increased ER stress. An siRNA and CRISPR screen targeting the druggable genome in combination with the ERK inhibitor SCH772984 was performed in three mutant KRAS cell lines and components of the ATR-CHK1 DDR were identified.

3.3. Drug resistance screening

Genome-scale CRISPR-Cas knockout is utilized to explore the mechanisms of pancreatic cancer development both *in vivo* and *in vitro*, overcoming drug resistance, and has identified essential genes in pancreatic cancer cell lines. Drug resistance screens have been performed in a variety of mouse and human cell lines as well as in mouse models for a range of chemotherapies (Table 1; [67–73]). In gemcitabine resistance, the mouse GeCKO(Genome-Scale CRISPR Knockout) v2 library pinpoints CCNL1's role via ERK/AKT/STAT3(signal transducer and activator of transcription 3) pathway [67], the kinome library shows CDK7(cyclin dependent kinase 7, human) inhibition sensitizes to chemotherapy [68], the RxG library reveals BCL-X_L(B-cell lymphoma-extra large, human) as a resistance factor to multiple drugs [69], the human GeCKO v2 library linked pyrimidine metabolism to NUC-1031 sensitivity [70], the human CRISPR activation library identified MTA3(metastasis associated 1 family member 3, human) as a promoter [71], the chromatin modifier library finds PRMT5(protein arginine methyltransferase 5, human) depletion enhances gemcitabine efficacy [72] and the GeCKO A library and SAM library uncovered ABCG2(ATP binding cassette subfamily G member 2, human) overexpression and HDAC1(histone deacetylase 1, human) activation in chemoresistance [73]. Although multiple studies have investigated the same therapeutic agents, none of the studies collected here have identified the same resistance genes. This may be explained by differences in CRISPR libraries, models, and treatment protocols as well as the tendency to focus on the validation of novel rather than known resistance genes. However, it also highlights the need for a standardized CRISPR screening protocol for the detection of resistance genes to facilitate the

Table 1
CRISPR/Cas9 Screening of drug resistance in pancreatic cancer.

Library	Model	Treatment	Findings	Ref.
mouse GeCKO v2 CRISPR knockout library, targeting 20611 genes	TB32047	50 nM gemcitabine (IC ₉₀) for TB32047 wild-type cells for 3 days, 5 rounds	The loss of CCNL1 activates the ERK/AKT/STAT3 survival pathway, causing cell resistance to gemcitabine treatment.	[67]
Mouse Brie kinome pooled library, targeting 920 PDAC-related genes	TB32047	gemcitabine (IC ₉₀ = 50 nM), or paclitaxel (IC ₇₀ = 10 nM) for 21 days.	CDK7 inhibition augments response to multidrug chemotherapy in pancreatic cancer	[68]
Therapeutic Genome (RxG) library, targeting 996 genes	AsPC-1	IC ₃₀ -IC ₅₀ of each drug (gemcitabine, 5-fluorouracil (5-FU), and niraparib) for 16 days	BCL-X _L induces resistance to gemcitabine, 5-FU, and niraparib	[69]
Human GeCKO v2 CRISPR knockout library, targeting 19050 genes	Mia PaCa-2, A2780	15 nM gemcitabine or 65 nM NUC-1031 for 14 days or 21 days	Pyrimidine metabolism pathway modifies sensitivity to NUC-1031. Low DCK correlates with resistance to gemcitabine but not NUC-1031.	[70]
Human CRISPR activation library, targeting 23430 genes	BxPC-3	2 nM gemcitabine for 3 days	MTA3 promoted gemcitabine resistance of PDAC cells by transcriptionally repressed CRIP2	[71]
Chromatin modifiers library, targeting 619 human genes	Orthotopic patient-derived xenograft (PDX)	gemcitabine (50 mg/kg or 100 mg/kg) for 5 weeks	PRMT5 depletion sensitizes to gemcitabine, PRMT5 inhibition impairs DNA repair resulting in synergistic accumulation of gemcitabine-induced DNA damage	[72]
Human GeCKO A library and SAM library for gene knockout and activation screening, targeting 23728 genes	Panc-1 and BxPC3	Gemcitabine (25 nM), Oxaliplatin (2.5 μ M), Irinotecan (500 nM or 250 nM), 5-FU (7.5 μ M or 5 μ M) for 14 days	ABCG2 overexpression resulted in resistance to chemotherapy, HDAC1-activated exhibited cell migration	[73]

comparison and validation of multiple studies. The NIST Genome Editing Consortium is actively working on the development of experimental benchmarks, guidelines, and terminology for gene editing (<https://www.nist.gov/programs-projects/nist-genome-editing-consortium>).

While the description of a standardized protocol is outside the scope of this review, although several excellent protocols are available ([74], <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-2687-9>, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xpro.2021.100390>), we would like to highlight several considerations that should be taken into account when reporting a CRISPR screen [75, 76]. Firstly, the model system must be clearly described, particularly how Cas9 is introduced and expressed. This may involve co-transduction of Cas9 and sgRNA or the generation of a stable Cas9-expressing cell line. Authors should specify whether retroviral transduction was

used—acknowledging its potential for nonspecific genomic integration and off-target effects—or whether integration was targeted to a safe harbor locus [77,78]. which reduces these concerns. In either case, it is good practice to investigate the introduction of Cas9 on cell phenotype, in particular drug sensitivity in the case of drug screening. In terms of library design, researchers have the choice of using pre-designed and validated libraries, such as the GeCKO [79], Brunello, and Brie libraries [80], or designing their own library. When researchers decide to design their own library, it is important to report on the design process, including the reference genome used, inclusion of positive and negative controls, number of sgRNAs per target, and sgRNA sequences. Additionally, they should consider making the library available on a public repository such as Addgene (<https://www.addgene.org/>). For assay design, the method of library delivery should be detailed, including the multiplicity of infection (MOI), the selection strategy (e.g., fluorescence-based or antibiotic resistance), and the achieved library coverage. For drug resistance screens, it is critical to include extensive information on the treatment schedule, drug concentrations, and the subculturing protocol as these are the factors that tend to vary most between screens. The sequencing platform and depth must be reported to allow assessment of data quality and coverage. Finally, bioinformatic analysis should include a complete description of the computational pipeline used, specifying the software, version numbers, and any other relevant parameters to enable reproducibility and comparison across studies.

3.4. Enhancing understanding of the tumor-immune microenvironment

Immune checkpoint blockade (ICB) therapy has demonstrated considerable therapeutic success in malignancies such as melanoma and non-small cell lung cancer [81,82]. However, its efficacy is constrained in pancreatic cancer, which is classified as infiltrated-excluded tumor immune microenvironment (I-E TIMEs) [83] and typified by a scarcity of CD8 + T cells and low expression levels of activation markers such as granzyme B (GZMB) and interferon-gamma (IFNG). This phenotype suggests an absence of robust adaptive T-cell responses, thereby conferring resistance to immune checkpoint inhibitors [84]. In a recent study, Gu et al. observed that the resistant to cytotoxic T lymphocyte (CTL)-mediated killing of mesenchymal-like (Mes) KPC3 pancreatic cancer cells was higher than parental epithelial-like (Epi) cells. Using CRISPR/Cas9 knockout screens to investigate this difference, they found specific regulators, including *Egfr* and *Mfge8*, which were highly expressed in mesenchymal cancer cells and caused resistance to immune cell-mediated killing [85].

To identify potential therapeutic targets within the immunosuppressive tumor microenvironment (TME) of PDAC, a CRISPR screening approach, focusing on the kinome and membranome, was employed using orthotopic PDAC models, reveals that receptor-interacting protein kinase 2 (RIPK2) plays a pivotal role in mediating resistance to immune-mediated cytotoxicity. Inhibition, either genetically or pharmacologically, of RIPK2 was found to enhance the susceptibility of PDAC to anti-programmed cell death protein 1 (anti-PD-1) immunotherapy, culminating in improved survival rates and potential tumor regression. Further mechanistic investigations indicated that ablation of tumor-intrinsic RIPK2 leads to disruption of the desmoplastic TME and subsequent restoration of major histocompatibility complex class I (MHC-I) levels on the tumor cell surface. This restoration is attributed to the inhibition of the NBR1-mediated autophagy-lysosomal degradation pathways. These findings collectively provide a compelling rationale for the integration of RIPK2 inhibitors with anti-PD-1 immunotherapeutic strategies as a novel combinatorial therapeutic approach for PDAC [86].

Mediator complex subunit 12 (human symbol: MED12, mouse symbol: Med12) has been identified as a key potent negative factor in the TME of PDAC through an *in vivo* epigenetic-focused CRISPR-Cas9 screen. *Med12* deficiency significantly enhanced the infiltration and cytotoxicity of immune cells, including CD8 + T cells, natural killer (NK) cells,

and NK1.1 + T cells in tumors, thereby increasing sensitivity to immune checkpoint blockade (ICB) therapy in PDAC mouse models. Mechanistically, MED12 inhibited endogenous retrotransposition elements marked by H3K9me3 (histone 3 lysine 9 trimethylation) by stabilizing the heterochromatin protein HP1A. The derepression of retrotransposition elements caused by *MED12* deficiency activated cytoplasmic nucleic acid sensing and subsequent activation of the type I interferon pathway, ultimately leading to a strong inflammatory TME [87].

Falcomata et al. identified a synergistic effect between trametinib (a MEK inhibitor) and nintedanib (a multi-kinase inhibitor) through comprehensive high-throughput drug screening. Their combined therapy induces cell cycle arrest, promotes cell death, and modulates the immunosuppressive secretome of cancer cells in a context-dependent manner, enhancing the sensitivity of mesenchymal PDAC to PD-L1 (programmed cell death 1 ligand 1) blockade [88].

3.5. Other applications

In vivo CRISPR screening, SCAF1 (SR-related CTD associated factor 1, human) and USP15 (ubiquitin specific peptidase 15, human) have been identified as the key drivers of pancreatic cancer progression. The loss of *USP15*, in particular, has been shown to regulate TGF- β , WNT, and NF- κ B signaling, indicating its role as a PDAC tumor suppressor [89]. Utilizing a metabolism-focused mouse sgRNA library targeting approximately 2900 genes, the pivotal role of autophagy in immune evasion and cell death has been uncovered, as evidenced by the significant reduction in tumor size following the loss of the *Hmbs* (hydroxymethylbilane synthase, mouse) gene *in vivo* [90]. Additionally, CRISPR/Cas9 knockout has been used to investigate the role of CAFs in PDAC. Kuhn et al., used an adeno-associated virus to knockout *Osmr* (oncostatin M receptor, mouse), *Tgfr2* (transforming growth factor, beta receptor II, mouse), and *Il1r1* (interleukin 1 receptor, type I, mouse) in CAFs in a mouse model that expressed Cas9 in fibroblasts. This mouse model had been created by crossing mice with a *Pdgfra*-driven Cre allele with mice with the *Rosa26-LSL-Cas9-EGFP* allele. The researchers were able to achieve over 85 % of single gene knockouts. They observed that knockout of *Osmr* or *Tgfr2* changed fibroblast polarisation to a more activated state [91]. While some of these studies predominantly utilized subcutaneous tumor models, the physiological relevance of orthotopic models and GEMMs cannot be overlooked.

4. The potential of CRISPR for clinical trials

In the context of pancreatic cancer research, various models have been developed to better understand the disease pathogenesis and test therapeutic interventions. Fig. 4 shows different functions in preclinical models. Isogenic cell lines, derived from a single ancestral cell line with specific genetic modifications, provide a controlled system to study the effects of specific genetic alterations without genetic heterogeneity, however they may not fully recapitulate the complexity of human tumors and lack the *in vivo* tumor microenvironment [92]. Orthotopic xenografts allow for the study of PDAC cell lines, organoids, tumoroids, PDXs in an *in vivo* setting, providing insights into tumor growth, metastasis, and response to therapy, but they may not accurately represent the human disease due to the use of immunocompromised mice, which lack an intact immune system [93]. GEMMs have been instrumental in providing a natural immune-competent context for tumorigenesis that closely mirrors human cancers in terms of histopathology, molecular characteristics and metastatic potential. Compared to allograft or xenograft models, which often lack heterogeneity and metastatic progression, GEMMs offer a more comprehensive platform for preclinical studies, but they can be time-consuming and expensive to develop, and there are still species-specific differences [94]. GEMMs are adequate for studying the overall *in vivo* effects of CRISPR-based therapies, including long-term outcomes and systemic immune responses.

Fig. 4. Different preclinical models used for CRISPR in PDAC research. Representative PDAC model systems are isogenic cell line, xenografts and GEMMs. Drug screening, gene selection and pathway uncover can be perform in isogenic cell lines. Xenografts allow for the study of drug testing, pathway uncover, gene selection and providing insights into tumor growth, metastasis, and response to therapy, GEMMs provide a more physiologically relevant model of human cancer, as they develop tumors in an immune-competent host. They can recapitulate the multistep nature of tumorigenesis and metastasis, offering insights into the disease's natural history. The success approaches in preclinical models have laid the groundwork for the first-in-human trials, which are designed to assess the tolerability, pharmacokinetics, and preliminary therapeutic effects of these novel interventions in a controlled and ethically regulated environment. Created with BioGDD.com [95].

However, organoid-based co-culture systems provide advantages in high-throughput screening and detailed mechanistic studies. In certain settings, such as when focusing on specific interactions between tumor and immune cells or when aiming for personalized medicine approaches, organoid co-culture systems may offer superior advantages. While GEMMs provide a comprehensive *in vivo* context, organoid co-culture systems offer detailed insights into cellular interactions and immune responses. Combining data from both models can provide a more holistic understanding of CRISPR-based therapies.

4.1. Isogenic cell line models of PDAC

CRISPR has been revealed as a multifunctional tool for generating isogenic *in vitro* models of PDAC [96–98]. Geurts and Clevers suggested that isogenic human disease models could be useful for understanding the molecular mechanisms underlying genetic variations and for developing new therapeutic strategies [14]. In a study targeting NOXA (phorbol-12-myristate-13-acetate-induced protein 1, human)-deficient isogenic models of PDAC, researchers have uncovered a novel pathway for drug-induced apoptosis. They identified a CBF β (core binding factor beta)/RUNX1 (RUNX family transcription factor 1) inhibitor through drug screening that was validated to act through RUNX1 and NOXA. Notably, RUNX1 is overexpressed in PDAC compared to that in normal pancreas. Pharmacological inhibition of RUNX1 significantly impeded tumor growth *in vivo* and in patient-derived PDAC organoids. This study revealed that RUNX1 loss alters the epigenetic landscape, leading to H3K27ac (Trimethylation of histone H3 lysine 27) enrichment at the NOXA promoter and triggering NOXA-dependent cell death. This mechanism offers a potential therapeutic approach for overcoming resistance to treatment in PDAC, thus addressing an unmet clinical need [99]. A longitudinal analysis using an isogenic model, the 10–22 cell line, was used to track the transition from pancreatic intraepithelial neoplasia (PanIN) to PDAC in mice. This study identified transient gene expression signatures throughout PDAC progression, with key roles played by HBP1 (HMG-box transcription factor 1, human), BACH1 (BTB domain, and CNC homologue 1, human). These findings provide insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying PDAC development and may inform future therapeutic strategies targeting the HBP1, BACH1, and RUNX3 (RUNX family transcription factor 3, human) networks during

PDAC progression [97]. Outside PDAC, CRISPR has been used to establish panels of non-cancerous isogenic knockout cell lines that can be used to study the effect of a single gene perturbation on tumor initiation. Additionally, these cell line panels can be combined with large-scale CRISPR knockout screens or high-throughput drug screens to obtain a wealth of information on topics such as double-hit tumor initiation and synthetic lethality [100–102].

4.2. Genetically engineered mouse models of PDAC

Given the high mortality rate of PDAC and the challenges of a poor response to current treatments, it is crucial to use preclinical models that accurately reflect the pathological features of human PDAC to better assess therapeutic strategies. Several GEMMs have been used in pancreatic cancer research, such as KC (Lox-Stop-Lox (LSL):Kras^{G12D}, Pdx1-CRE) and KPCC (Kras^{G12D/+}; Trp53^{R172H/R172H}, P48-Cre) [103]. LSL-Kras^{G12D}, LSL-Trp53^{R172H}, and Pdx1-Cre (KPC) models are the most widely used GEMMs in preclinical pancreatic cancer research. The initiation of pancreatic tumorigenesis, driven by endogenous Kras^{G12D} expression in the context of Trp53^{R172H}, rapidly progresses to form locally invasive and metastatic PDAC in mice, this model reveals the synergistic onset of invasive carcinoma with extensive metastatic potential, closely modeling human disease [104]. AMG 510, the first Kras (G12C) inhibitor in clinical development, has undergone preclinical analyses in immune-competent mice, these analyses utilized syngeneic tumor models generated by CRISPR technology, which resulted in the regression of CT-26 Kras(G12C) tumors [105]. A high-efficiency pipeline for PDAC GEMMs has been developed using a single "workhorse" mouse strain with adult pancreatic Cas9 expression under the p48 promoter. This method employs adeno-associated virus (AAV) to deliver multiplexed guide RNAs (sgRNAs) to induce HDR of the oncogenic Kras (G12D) allele and CRISPR-induced disruptions of cooperating alleles (*Trp53*, *Lkb1* (liver kinase B1, mouse) and *Arid1A* (AT-rich interaction domain 1A, mouse)). The resulting GEMMs develop a spectrum of PDAC precursor lesions, such as PanIN and intraductal papillary mucinous neoplasm (IPMN), which progress to PDAC. Next-generation sequencing verifies the HDR of the Kras^{G12D} allele and the induction of indel mutations in targeted tumor suppressor genes. This streamlined approach offers a facile and autochthonous platform for studying the PDAC

genome, utilizing a single mouse strain and optimal AAV serotypes for in vivo gene editing, facilitating the investigation of PDAC genetics and potential therapeutic targets. [106]. *ARID1A*(human)-deficient tumors exhibit heightened mutational burden, T-cell infiltration, and PD-L1 upregulation, responding favorably to anti-PD-L1 therapy. This implicates *ARID1A* loss in modulating tumor mutational landscapes and potentially synergizing with immunotherapies [107]. Pancreatic Cas9 mice (Pdx1-Cre; (LSL)-*Kras*^{G12D}; LSL-Cas9-GFP mice) have also been used to perform small-scale CRISPR knockout screens, further expanding the possible applications of GEMMs [89]. GEMMs have become a cornerstone in the preclinical assessment of immunotherapeutic strategies and examination of immune responses elicited by therapeutic interventions in PDAC. These models have consistently provided valuable insights into the design and execution of numerous clinical trials, offering a robust framework for translating bench-to-bedside immunotherapeutic approaches.

4.3. Translating results from CRISPR screening

CRISPR screening has been used to identify novel targets and biomarkers in cancer research, leading to the development of targeted therapies. In a phase I clinical trial, CRISPR-Cas9 has been employed to engineer T cells from patients with advanced, refractory cancer, aiming to enhance the natural antitumor immune response. It targeted the endogenous T cell receptor (TCR) and the immune checkpoint molecule PD-1 to improve the functionality and persistence of engineered T cells and introduced a synthetic TCR transgene (NY-ESO-1) for cancer cell recognition. Three patients with refractory myeloma or metastatic sarcoma received infusions of these engineered T cells. Three genes (*TRAC* (T cell receptor alpha constant, human), *TRBC*(T cell receptor beta constant, human) and *PDCD1*(programmed cell death 1, human)) were deleted to improve antitumor immunity and enhance targeting. The engineered T cells demonstrated high specificity for targeted loci, although rare off-target edits were identified. Single-cell RNA sequencing revealed a diverse mutational landscape among the

engineered T cells. Notably, the edited T cells engrafted and persisted in all three patients for at least 9 months, a significantly longer duration than observed in previous trials. No clinical toxicities were associated with the engineered T cells, and chromosomal translocations observed in vitro decreased post-infusion. Biopsies confirmed T cell trafficking to tumor sites in all patients. These findings underscore the safety and feasibility of CRISPR-Cas9-based T cell engineering for cancer immunotherapy [108]. Phase Ib/II clinical trials (clinicaltrials.gov; trial NCT04581473 and NCT04581473) are currently recruiting patients to assess the efficacy, safety, and pharmacokinetics of CT041, an autologous CAR T-cell therapy, in patients with advanced gastric or gastroesophageal junction adenocarcinoma and pancreatic cancer, resulting in a reduction in lung metastatic lesions [109]. In summary, CRISPR/Cas-based diagnostics has translated into tangible clinical advancements, accelerated drug development, and provided deeper insights into disease mechanisms, thereby enabling more precise treatment strategies.

5. Potential limitations of CRISPR/Cas9 editing and important considerations in experimental design and application

While CRISPR/Cas9 technology has significantly enhanced gene editing, it is not without its limitations. The following section discusses limitations, and possibilities to overcome these limitations, considering the genetic background of pancreatic cancer, off-target effects, and delivery of the CRISPR/Cas9 system to the target cell (Fig. 5). Genome editing by CRISPR/Cas9 induces p53-mediated DNA damage response and the cell cycle arrest [110]. This can lead to the selection against cells with functional p53 pathway. This is of importance, as p53 mutation occurs in 50–75 % of human PDAC following *KRAS* mutation [111], and in a heterogeneous cell population may lead to a selection of cells with pre-existing p53 mutations. Upregulation of the p53 pathway upon introduction of Cas9, especially in TP53 WT cell lines, has been observed both at the mRNA and the protein level [112]. Large variation in mutant recovery for a given target sequence between the cell lines is still not

	limitations	solutions
selection against p53	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> gene-editing induces cell arrest selection advantage mtKRAS sex-related differences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> monitor editing efficacy adapt study design
off-target effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> system-based quality sgRNA quality reference genome 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> base/prime-editors, modified Cas9, anti-CRISPR protein in silico prediction check natural variants, use WES data host
delivery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> electroporation (low efficacy, high cell death) viral (packaging size, targeting tissue, stable expression) lipid nanoparticles (targeting) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> switch to viral or lipid nanoparticles smaller Cas9 variants, modify viral capsid, injection in tissue modification lipid layer

Fig. 5. Limitations of CRISPR/Cas9 technology, The three primary limitations of CRISPR/Cas9 technology are selection against p53, off-target effects, delivery challenges, along with their respective potential solutions.

clear, and in addition to the Cas DNA binding and cleavage, mutational status of the p53 may be the cause of the cell cycle arrest [113]. Wild-type KRAS can also hamper the growth of Cas9-edited cells, potentially conferring advantage to the pre-existing KRAS-mutant cells, and these selection events have been observed across cell types and CRISPR/Cas9 delivery methods [114]. Currently, gene editing for the treatment of PDAC is predominantly explored in the setting of engineered T cell therapy where the risk of pre-existing TP53 or KRAS mutations is relatively low. However, should CRISPR/Cas9 editing be targeted at PDAC cells, monitoring of patients with pre-existing p53 and KRAS mutations may be necessary.

Another layer of complexity is introduced with sex-related differences in the p53 gene network. p53 is differentially regulated in both healthy and cancer samples between females and males, as many genes in the network are X-chromosome regulated [115]. More than 100 genes showed sex-bias in a CRISPR-Cas9 knockout screen and sex-based difference was observed between p53 WT and mutant cell lines [116]. Cell lines from female donors had higher fold activation of p53, with more DNA loci and larger number of TP53-inactivating subclonal mutations. In contrast, the difference between Cas9 activity between p53-WT and p53-MUT was larger in males. After functional enrichment analysis authors found that LEF1 (lymphoid enhancer binding factor 1, human), FOXO4 (forkhead box O4, human), SOX9 (SRY-box transcription factor 9, human symbol) and RYBP (RING1 and YY1 binding protein, human) transcription factors may be the drivers of the potential sex bias. Unfortunately, many major studies in the field do not report the sex of the cell lines, organoids or animals used. These findings urge for the careful consideration of patient sex in further clinical applications of CRISPR-Cas9 editing.

While the CRISPR/Cas9 system has the potential to perform highly specific gene edits, it is not perfect and off-target effects may occur. In the case of *in vitro* experiments this can lead to false results which, although potentially introducing bias, may be mitigated by the use of multiple sgRNAs for the same target. However, off-target effects can have much more severe consequences in a clinical setting where they may lead to treatment failure or predispose patients to adverse outcomes. Several computational methods have been developed to predict off-target effects *in silico* (reviewed here [117]), but the specificity of sgRNAs is also heavily dependent on the quality of the reference genome that is used. Naturally occurring and cancer-related genetic variation has been shown to drastically affect CRISPR/Cas9 activity and specificity [118–121]. Awareness of naturally occurring variants will improve sgRNA design [122], but may not be sufficient in genomes with high variation as is the case in pancreatic cancer. It is therefore recommended to use the to-be edited genome for the design of sgRNAs or evaluate sgRNA specificity when this is not feasible (for example when using pre-designed CRISPR libraries). Additionally, numerous efforts have been made to reduce CRISPR/Cas9 off-target effects by modifying the Cas9 protein [123,124], the use of prime/base editors [125,126], and addition of anti-CRISPR proteins (reviewed in [127,128]).

A major limitation in the *in vivo* application of CRISPR/Cas9 is delivery of the CRISPR system to the pancreas and into the target cells. Current delivery systems fall into one of three categories: physical delivery, most notably electroporation; viral vector delivery, including adeno(associated)virus and lentivirus; and non-viral vector delivery such as liposomal particles. While *in vivo* electroporation has been used to transfect a CRISPR/Cas9 vector into the pancreas, the achieved efficacy rates were very poor [129]. Electroporation has also been used to create CRISPR/Cas9-engineered T cells in an *ex vivo* setting in a clinical trial by introducing ribonucleoprotein complexes of Cas9 protein with sgRNAs targeting TRAC, TRBC, and PDCD1 [108]. Editing efficacy varied between 15 % and 45 %, with 20 % having persistent di- and trigenic alterations. The difficulties of performing electroporation *in vitro*, the associated induction of cell death due to permeabilization of the membrane, and low efficacy makes this technique unfavorable for *in vivo* applications.

The most commonly used method to deliver the CRISPR/Cas9 system to the target cells is by a viral vector. Viral vectors include adeno-associated virus (AAV), adenovirus, and lentivirus. AAV is preferred in *in vivo* settings because of its low immunogenicity and has been used in clinical trials [130]. It is a small non-pathogenic virus that cannot replicate independently which contributes to its safety. The virus can be made to carry the Cas9 gene and a gRNA by cloning it into the viral genome. However, due to the small size of the AAV, insertion of transgenes is restricted to a maximum size of 4.7 kb. With the size of the commonly used *Streptococcus pyogenes* Cas9 being 4.2 kb, inclusion of one or more gRNAs, tags, or templates for HDR is severely limited. Smaller Cas variants such as *Staphylococcus aureus* Cas9 (saCas9, 3.2 kb), *Neisseria meningitidis* Cas9 (Nme2Cas9, 3.3 kb), or Cas13b (3.3 kb) may provide alternatives that allow for insertion of longer sequences [131, 132].

Viral vectors integrate Cas9 into the host genome which induces stable expression of the protein. Depending on the aim of the treatment, this may be beneficial, but it also carries the risk of off-target effects and alteration of non-target tissues. To direct the viral vector to its target tissue, receptor-binding motifs on the capsid surface can be modified to create tissue tropism [133,134]. Alternatively, direct pancreatic injection, as opposed to systemic injection, may be sufficient to retain the virus in the pancreas [135]. In mouse models, Pdx1-Cre mice crossed with LSL-Cas9 mice have been used to create mice with pancreas-specific expression of Cas9 which were then transduced with pooled AV containing the gRNA library [89].

Some of the limitations of viral vectors can be overcome by lipid nanoparticles (LNPs). In contrast to viral vectors, LNPs can be loaded with ribonucleoproteins such as Cas9 with associated gRNA. This allows for transient expression of Cas9 and thereby decreases the risk of off-target genome modifications. Additionally, LNPs can carry a larger payload, have a lower immunogenicity, and are easier to assemble compared to viral vectors [132,136]. Similar to AAVs, delivery to the target organ remains a limitation. Modification of the lipid layer can create tissue tropism which enables systemic injection, but this also exposes the LNPs to a host of factors which may decrease efficacy such as clearance by the kidneys or the mononuclear phagocytic system, interaction with biomolecules in the blood that affect stability, size-dependent extravasation, and cellular uptake. Each of these factors requires careful consideration to develop an optimal LNP. Direct injection into the pancreas or intraperitoneal injection may circumvent some of these factors. Nevertheless, intraperitoneal injection of an anti-EGFR labeled LNP containing Cas9/sgKRAS and ABE-sgP53 to restore KRAS and TP53 function in a Panc1 cell-implanted xenograft mouse model has shown an approximate 63 % gene editing efficiency and significantly sensitized the cells to gemcitabine highlighting the potential of this technique [137].

6. Conclusions

The application of CRISPR/Cas9 genome engineering has considerably advanced our understanding of PDAC at both the genetic and molecular levels. This technology has not only enhanced our ability to model disease progression through isogenic cell lines and GEMMs but has also facilitated the identification of critical genes and pathways involved in PDAC initiation, progression, and response to therapy. Comprehensive analysis of CRISPR/Cas9 screens has uncovered the multifaceted roles of genes in pancreatic cancer progression, underscoring the potential for targeting these genes to improve therapeutic outcomes. Furthermore, integrating CRISPR/Cas9 with immunotherapeutic strategies has demonstrated promising results, indicating that modulating the tumor microenvironment through CRISPR/Cas9 interventions could sensitize PDAC to immune checkpoint inhibitors and improve patient outcomes.

The translation of aforementioned preclinical findings into clinical practice is underway, as exemplified by the ongoing development and

testing of novel therapeutic strategies, including CAR-T cell therapies. The ability to manipulate the genome with precision has opened new avenues for personalized medicine. Continued refinement of CRISPR/Cas9 technologies, coupled with a deeper understanding of the PDAC genome, will be instrumental in overcoming the challenges associated with this aggressive cancer. The progress made so far is a testament to the power of genomics-driven medicine and offers optimism for the future of cancer research and therapeutics. CRISPR/Cas9-based approaches may become a mainstay in our arsenal against PDAC in the near future, though further investigation and clinical validation are highly warranted, offering new hope for patients with this devastating disease.

Author contributions according to CRediT taxonomy

Conceptualization: CP; Funding acquisition: RG, CP; Supervision: CP, NW; Writing -original draft: YL, JS, YRT; Writing -review & editing: NW, JG, MFB, HL, TC, CP, RG.

Declaration of Competing Interest

On behalf of my co-authors, I would like to declare that we have nothing to disclose.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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